

DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING THE GRAMMATICAL FEATURES OF CONJUNCTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7314538>

Abstract. *In this article, one of the important sections of linguistics, conjunctions in grammar and the difficulties encountered in teaching them, and also in teaching English, are discussed and analyzed. In addition, reviews and some comments by famous scholars and students are included as an addition.*

Key words: *teaching, difficulties, conjunction.*

ТРУДНОСТИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИМ ОСОБЕННОСТЯМ СОЮЗОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются и анализируются один из важных разделов языкознания, союзы в грамматике и трудности, возникающие при их обучении, а также при обучении английскому языку. Кроме того, в качестве приложения включены обзоры и некоторые комментарии известных ученых и студентов.*

Ключевые слова: *учение, трудности, конъюнкция.*

English language is a global language as no language is spoken as wide as English Language nowadays. [6] In many countries such as Canada, Australia, New Zealand, Malaysia, India, and Singapore, English language has been used as their second language, but in Asian countries such as Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan, it has been used as a foreign language. In learning or teaching foreign language grammar certainly, we come across some difficulties in teaching. One of them is conjunctions, because the Uzbek language is a language rich in synonyms and antonyms. Even in conjunctions, several options are found that replace each other. This is, I think, the main reason why we have some challenges in using conjunctions in English. As you know, coordinating conjunction 'but', it means 'ammo, lekin, biroq, shunday bo'lsa ham' in Uzbek language at the same time. Also the adverb "until" functions as a subordinating conjunction, it can be translated 'gacha' in Uzbek language. However, "till" is also used in the similar meaning. Furthermore, there are some difficulties in conjunction, such as pronunciation, punctuation, sentence structure, influence of mother tongue and word order.

"Conjunctions allow you to form complex, elegant sentences and avoid the chopiness of multiple short sentences. Make sure that the phrases joined by conjunctions are parallel (share the same structure).[4]

Incorrect - I work quickly and careful.

Correct - I work quickly and carefully." [5]

When the correlative conjunction “neither/nor” is used in Uzbek, the verb can also be negative. But in English, when used in a linking sentence, the verb must be in the present form. Under the influence of the mother tongue, students make mistakes and use the verb in the negative form.

Lots of scientists observed and learned about conjunction and its functions in English language. According Ana Cristina Lahuerta Martinez’s thoughts there is scant information on the use of cohesive devices by ESL/EFL writers across grade levels. As our second aim, we intend to examine to which extent the use of conjunctions might associate with distinct grade EFL writers. The comparison between third and fourth graders’ writings allows us to identify how the use of conjunctions develop within a school setting and may deepen our understanding of the deployment of cohesive items in EFL writing. [1] Also there are several difficulties in listening. “It is the obligation for English teacher to teach students how to be good listener. As the result, the teacher should face some problems in teaching listening process. It has been claimed that over 50 percent of the time that students spend functioning in a foreign language will be devoted to listening (Nunan, 1998) cited in Nation and Newton (2009:37).” [2] Furthermore, “...for the most part, within the classroom, any mention of grammar causes the student moments of discomfort and sometimes even terror. Many teachers have tried to make grammar teaching a non-threatening, imaginative and useful activity within the English curriculum.... Previous studies on students' and teachers' attitudes and perceptions of grammar instruction in the context of language teaching and learning suggest a disparity between students and teachers. While students favour formal and explicit grammar instruction and error correction, teachers favour communicative activities with less conscious focus on grammar (e.g., Brindley 1984; Kumaravadivelu 1991; Leki 1995; Schultz 1996, 2001; Spratt 1999).

In teaching grammar, three areas have to be considered: grammar as rules, grammar as form, and grammar as resource. For many L2 learners, learning grammar often means learning the rules of grammar and having an intellectual knowledge of grammar. Teachers often believe that this will provide the generative basis on which learners can build their knowledge and will be able to use the language eventually. For them, prescribed rules give a kind of security.” [3]

REFERENCES

1. Ana Cristina Lahuerta Martínez ‘Use of conjunctions in the compositions of secondary education students’
2. “Analyzing teacher’s difficulties in teaching listening” Suhud Aryana, Yanuarti Apsari
3. “Difficulties in teaching and learning Grammar in an EFL context” Abdu Mohammed Al-Mekhlafi PhD., College of Education, Sultan Qaboos University, Oman rayan3@gmail.com Ramani Perur Nagaratnam PhD., Ministry of Manpower, Oman “International Journal of Instruction e-ISSN: 1308-1470 • www.e-iji.net” July 2011 • Vol.4, No.2 p-ISSN: 1694-609X
4. https://www.grammarly.com/blog/conjunctions/?gclid=CjwKCAjwtp2bBhAGEiwoAOZZTuC_oPvOwKrIELTmWOH9iXRiYZa-Pb_fT6e9_qu2sz0TwwhepBrthHRoC3HUQAvD_BwE&gclid=aw.ds
5. <https://www.hogwartsishere.com/library/book/20224/>
6. J. Melitz, “English as a global language,” in *The Palgrave handbook of economics and language*, Springer, 2016, pp. 583–615.